

Mathematical Modelling of Water Quality in River Type Aquatic Systems

Kiran Malviya¹, Anil Rajput², D.S. Solanki³

¹Research Scholar, Department of Mathematics, Barkatullah University, Bhopal, India.

²Professor and OSD, Department of Higher Education Govt. of MP Bhopal, India.

³Retired Professor, Department of Mathematics, I.E.H.E., Bhopal, India.

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 22 June 2026	Water is one of the main elements of the environment which determine the existence of life on the earth, affect the climate and limit the development of civilization. Water quality is critical for environmental sustainability, especially in river ecosystems. Pollution from agricultural runoff, industrial discharge, and domestic sewage severely affects aquatic health. Proper assessment of the degree of water quality is the basis for conservation and rational utilization of water resources. Water quality in river, lakes and dams is undergoing continuous degradation caused by natural processes resulting from eutrophication and due to anthropogenic reasons. One of the tools that are used to solve problems of river water pollution is the mathematical modelling. Mathematical models help predict pollutant behavior and guide water quality management. This research presents a novel mathematical model for simulating the quality of river water in terms of pollutant concentration. We formulate a one-dimensional advection diffusion-reaction equation, incorporating source terms and decay, to describe pollutant transport along a river. The model is intended for theoretical understanding and can be applied where data is limited. Results demonstrate how different parameters affect pollutant distribution.
Corresponding Author: Kiran Malviya	
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1. INTRODUCTION

According to World Meteorological Organization, Only around 0.5% of Earth's water is accessible and usable as freshwater, and climate change poses a serious threat to this limited supply (Citaristi 2022). Quality of water is the most important physical support in life. Peoples need water for feeding, metabolism processing, cleaning, sporting, bathing, irrigation, industrial, agricultural, etc. To get the best support from water, peoples have to consider the water quality. Water quality depends on the chemicals substances and biological creatures those are existed in the water. Sometimes water contains some dangerous microbiological creatures or chemicals substances. Those not only affect in water used by humans, but also for some creatures those lives in the water (Ahmad et al. 2020). In India, many aquifers are being contaminated by a host of human activities, such as sewage disposal, refuse dumps, pesticides and chemical fertiliser contamination, industrial effluent discharges, and toxic waste disposal (Singh et al. 2016). The study of rivers water quality is extremely important. This issue is more important when the

ivers are one of the main sources of water supply for drinking, agriculture, industry etc. Unfortunately, river pollution has become one of the most important problems in the environment (Benedini and Tsakiris 2013). The water quality of watershed systems is affected by high anthropogenic pressures, including domestic wastewater discharges and industrial and agricultural activities (Zadeh et al. 2022). The deterioration of the water environment has led to the reduction of available water resources and damaged a healthy aquatic ecosystem. The water environment system is very complicated and depends on weather, water body hydraulic characteristics, pollutant discharge, and the aquatic biological impact. Therefore, it is necessary to predict the water quality evolution process (Liu et al. 2021). The various reasons of water pollution leads to degradation of its quality and thus rendering it toxic to human and to the environment (Pariyar and Kafle 2025). The main purpose of the water quality monitoring system is to generate sufficient and timely information to establish water quality management plans and make environmental policies (Telci et al. 2009). Mathematical

modeling, involves the transformation of the system under study from its natural environment to Mathematical environment in terms of abstract symbols and equations. The symbols have well defined meaning and can be manipulated following a rigid set of rules or "Mathematical calculi". Mathematical models can be classified into various types depending on the nature of the variables. Mathematical models are recognized as effective tools that could help examine environmental, economic, and ecological impacts of alternative pollution control and resources-conservation actions, and thus aid planners or decision makers in formulating cost effective management policies(Zeidan 2017). River hydrodynamics is a complex process, which presents a turbulent flow. the problem of reducing pollution and improving water quality can be solved by using the appropriate mathematical models(Ciufudean et al. 2008).

1.1 Key Components in Water Pollution Models

- **Pollutant Sources** Understanding the sources of pollution is essential for accurate modelling. Pollutants are generally categorized into:
 - **1.Point Sources:** These are identifiable, fixed sources of pollution such as industrial effluents, sewage outfalls, and wastewater treatment plants. Mathematical models use specific discharge rates and pollutant concentration values from these sources to predict pollution spread.
 - **2.Non-point sources:** Non-point pollution, such as runoff from agricultural land, urban areas, and storm water systems, is more diffuse and challenging to model. it requires sophisticated approaches to estimate pollutant loads from large distributed areas.
- **Transport Mechanisms** The spread of pollutants in water bodies is influenced by various physical processes:
 - **1.Advection:** This is the transport of pollutants driven by the flow of water. Rivers, streams, and ocean currents all contribute to the advection of pollutants.
 - **2.Diffusion:** Diffusion occurs due to concentration gradients, where pollutants move from areas of higher concentration to areas of lower concentration. In aquatic systems, diffusion tends to be slower than advection but is crucial in smaller, stagnant water bodies.
 - **3.Dispersion:** Dispersion is a combination of advection and diffusion. It accounts for the spreading of pollutants in both the direction of flow and perpendicular to it, making it important in modelling the overall extent of contamination.
- **Decay and Degradation** Once pollutants enter water bodies, they undergo natural processes of decay and degradation:
 - **1.Biodegradation:** Microorganisms in water bodies break down organic pollutants, such as sewage and

agricultural runoff. this process can be modeled using first-order or higher-order kinetics.

- **2.Chemical Reactions and Photolysis:** Pollutants can also undergo chemical transformation or breakdown due to sunlight (photolysis), which is particularly relevant for pollutants like pesticides and some industrial chemicals(Ossaiugbo et al. 2024).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Rauch et al. studied mathematically the problem of surface water pollution, such as eutrophication, acute and chronic toxicity(Rauch et al. 1998). Marusic presented a mathematical model for analysing the hydrodynamics and pollutant dispersion in river-type systems. They were able to report changes in the pollutant concentration in the river with time(Marusic 2012). Pochai et al. proposed a mathematical model for optimally controlling pollutant level in wastewater discharge that would reduce initial water treatment cost to a minimum cost(Pochai et al. 2006). Pimpunchat et al. have presented a mathematical model of pollution in river, they presented a simple model and provided some analytical solutions at steady state flows, and investigate the effect of aeration on the degradation of Pollutant, their model consists of a pair of coupled reaction-diffusion-advection equations for the Pollutant and dissolved oxygen concentrations Advection-diffusion equation(Pimpunchat et al. 2009). Mathematical water quality models date back to the well known model in 1925 of Streeter and Phelps; where they described the balance of dissolved oxygen in rivers(Kaushik et al. 2012). Using iron polluted water has negative consequences for human health. This is discussed in(Marusic et al. 2012). Yadav et al. presented an analytical solution to the advection-dispersion equation while incorporating spatially dependent parameters, such as variable dispersion and advection coefficients. the study improved the understanding of how spatial heterogeneity impacts transport processes(Yadav and Roy 2020). The authors merged it with Bagmati-river to control the pollution. and found that one dimensional method is used to remove pollutants from the river. and also found that a mathematical model can make a complex situation simple. it has been closely observed that the mathematical model helps us make predictions and find a better understanding of the real world problem(Singh et al. 2022). Paudel et al. presented a coupled system of advection-dispersion equations based water pollution model. that incorporates different parameters. and constructed analytical solutions for mathematical models. and observed the concentrations of pollutant and dissolved oxygen in the river. one dimensional model is used to observe the concentrations by taking the dimensions along the length of the river. the investigation of steady states is made possible by taking into account the elimination of pollutants by aeration. in this model coupled advection-dispersion equations are solved by taking dispersion coefficient(Paudel et al. 2022). Maisarah

halimi et al. 2024 focuses on finding the analytical solution to the one-dimensional ADE with spatially dependent diffusion and velocity for the case where the pollutant is instantaneously introduced to the river (Halimi and Isa 2024). Kafle et al. focused on the one dimensional Advection-Dispersion Equation (ADE) to study the dynamics of concentration of water pollution when the pollutants at the source is increasing uniformly and exponentially (Kafle et al. 2025). Recently, a number of mathematical models on river pollution have been appeared in literature (Ahmed Abdullah Hamoud and Ghadle 2018), (Ahmed A. Hamoud and K. P. Ghadle 2018), (Ahmed A. Hamoud and K. Ghadle 2018), (Simon and Koya 2015), (Simon and Koya 2017).

3. OBJECTIVE

This paper proposes a simple, original mathematical model to simulate pollutant transport in a river using a partial differential equation (PDE) framework. The model can be used in hypothetical cases where data is unavailable.

4. MATHEMATICAL MODELLING

We consider the following 1D advection-diffusion-reaction equation:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} - v \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} - kC + S(x, t)$$

where:

- $C(x, t)$ is the pollutant concentration
- D is the dispersion coefficient
- v is the river flow velocity
- k is the decay rate
- $S(x, t)$ is the pollutant source term

5. ASSUMPTIONS

- One-dimensional river flow
- Constant flow velocity and dispersion
- Single pollutant source
- No sediment or vertical variation considered

6. STEADY-STATE ANALYSIS

Assuming steady state ($\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = 0$), we simplify the equation:

$$D \frac{d^2 C}{dx^2} - v \frac{dC}{dx} - kC + S(x) = 0$$

This second-order ordinary differential equation is solved under boundary conditions to estimate pollutant concentration.

7. ANALYTICAL SOLUTION OF THE MATHEMATICAL MODEL

The governing advection–dispersion–reaction equation for pollutant transport in a river is given by

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} - v \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} - kC + S(x, t)$$

where $C(x, t)$ is the pollutant concentration, D is the dispersion coefficient, v is the river flow velocity, k is the decay coefficient, and $S(x, t)$ is the pollutant source term.

7.1 Steady-State Condition

Under steady-state conditions,

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = 0$$

Therefore,

$$D \frac{d^2 C}{dx^2} - v \frac{dC}{dx} - kC + S(x) = 0$$

Assuming a constant pollutant source $S(x) = S_0$,

$$D \frac{d^2 C}{dx^2} - v \frac{dC}{dx} - kC + S_0 = 0$$

7.2 Homogeneous Solution

The homogeneous equation is

$$D \frac{d^2 C}{dx^2} - v \frac{dC}{dx} - kC = 0$$

Assume

$$C = e^{rx}$$

Substituting into Equation (5) gives

$$Dr^2 - vr - k = 0$$

The characteristic roots are

$$r_{1,2} = \frac{v \pm \sqrt{v^2 + 4Dk}}{2D}$$

Thus, the homogeneous solution becomes

$$C_h(x) = Ae^{r_1 x} + Be^{r_2 x}$$

where A and B are arbitrary constants.

7.3 Particular Solution

For a constant source term,

$$C_p = \frac{S_0}{k}$$

7.4 General Solution

Combining the homogeneous and particular solutions,

$$C(x) = Ae^{r_1 x} + Be^{r_2 x} + \frac{S_0}{k}$$

This equation represents the pollutant concentration distribution along the river.

8. BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

The following boundary conditions are assumed:

$$C(0) = 100 \text{ mg/L}$$

$$C(L) = 0$$

where L is the river length under consideration.

Applying these boundary conditions determines the unknown constants A and B .

9. HYPOTHETICAL CASE STUDY

We consider:

- $v = 0.5 \text{ m/s}$
- $D = 10 \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$
- $k = 0.02/\text{s}$
- $S(x)$ at 1 km with 100 mg/L concentration

The characteristic roots are calculated as

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$$r = \frac{0.5 \pm \sqrt{0.25 + 0.8}}{20}$$

which gives

$$r_1 = 0.0762$$

and

$$r_2 = -0.0262$$

Substituting these values into the general solution,

$$C(x) = Ae^{0.0762x} + Be^{-0.0262x} + \frac{S_0}{0.02}$$

The results indicate that pollutant concentration decreases downstream because of dispersion and natural decay processes.

Steady-state concentration profile predicted by 1D Advection-Dispersion model with first-order decay. The pollutant concentration decreases exponentially from 100 mg/L at the source ($x = 0$) to 70.7 mg/L at 50 km downstream. The model indicates 29.3% natural purification over the 50 km river stretch.

10. MODEL INTERPRETATION

The model demonstrates that:

- Advection transports pollutants downstream.
- Dispersion spreads pollutants throughout the river.
- Decay reduces pollutant concentration over time.
- Source loading increases concentration near the discharge point.
- Pollutant concentration decreases with increasing distance from the source.

11. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The model shows:

- High decay rate reduces pollution rapidly
- Low dispersion keeps pollution localized
- Faster velocity spreads pollutants quickly

12. APPLICATIONS

- Teaching basic water quality modelling
- Early-stage environmental assessment
- Modelling in data-scarce areas

13. CONCLUSION

Mathematical models are indispensable tools in understanding and managing river water quality. They provide insights into the movement, degradation, and impacts of pollutants, guiding policies for sustainable water management. Mathematical models will continue to play a key role in protecting water resources for future generations. The proposed model captures essential features of pollutant transport using a simple PDE. It is adaptable for theoretical and teaching purposes and can be extended using real data.

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